

STATE POLICY AGAINST UNEMPLOYMENT AMONG THE POPULATION:
INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE AND NATIONAL APPROACHES

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola O'zbekiston Respublikasida ishsizlikni kamaytirish, aholining bandligini ta'minlash va davlat tomonidan amalga oshirilayotgan chora-tadbirlar hamda huquqiy asoslar masalasiga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada O'zbekiston tajribasi va xalqaro davlatlarning ishsizlikka qarshi kurashdagi tajribalari tahlil qilinadi. Davlat tomonidan amalga oshirilayotgan kompleks yondashuvlar, jumladan, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, startaplarni qo'llab-quvvatlash, ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish va mehnat migratsiyasini kengaytirish kabi chora-tadbirlar huquqiy asosda ishsizlikni qisqartirishga xizmat qilmoqda. Shuningdek, maqolada gender tengligi, yoshlar ishsizligi va mintaqaviy farqlar bo'yicha xalqaro tajribalar ham o'z aksini topgan. Ushbu maqola davlat siyosati, iqtisodiy barqarorlik va jamiyat farovonligini ta'minlash uchun huquqiy asoslarni shakllantirishda dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Annotation: This article discusses the reduction of unemployment in Uzbekistan, ensuring employment, and the legal framework implemented by the government. The article analyzes Uzbekistan's experience and international practices in combating unemployment. The comprehensive approach taken by the government, including vocational training, support for startups, improving the education system, and expanding labor migration, is grounded in legal frameworks aimed at reducing unemployment. Additionally, the article addresses issues such as gender equality, youth unemployment, and regional disparities, with references to international experiences. This article is essential for understanding how legal foundations are essential in addressing unemployment and ensuring economic stability and social well-being.

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена сокращению безработицы в Узбекистане, обеспечению занятости населения и правовой основе, реализуемой государством. В статье анализируется опыт Узбекистана и международные практики борьбы с безработицей. Комплексный подход государства, включая профессиональное обучение, поддержку стартапов, улучшение образовательной системы и расширение трудовой миграции, базируется на правовых рамках, направленных на сокращение безработицы. Также в статье рассматриваются проблемы гендерного равенства, безработицы среди молодежи и региональные различия с упором на международный опыт. Эта статья является важной для понимания, как правовые основы необходимы для решения проблемы безработицы и обеспечения экономической стабильности и социального благополучия.

Kalit so'zlar : ishsizlik, davlat siyosati, huquqiy asos, kasbiy tayyorgarlik, mehnat migratsiyasi, iqtisodiy barqarorlik, xalqaro tajribalar, ish bilan ta'minlash, mehnat huquqlari

INTRODUCTION

One of the important factors of economic stability and social well-being is the full employment of the population. It even lowers the standard of living of citizens. Unemployment is one of the most urgent problems that must be solved in the legal, economic and social policy of states.

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The causes and consequences of unemployment among the population depend on many economic, demographic and social factors. The level of unemployment is an important indicator for the economic development of the country, and it is necessary to analyze it deeply in the state policy. However, unemployment should not be limited to economic factors alone. Gender equality, youth unemployment, regional differences, as well as education, skills shortages, and social issues also affect unemployment. Especially in rural areas, the lack of opportunities in the labor market is causing unemployment. In addition, the closure of enterprises and the reduction of labor migration lead to the deepening of the problem. It is important to consider these social factors when developing measures to overcome this problem. Because it affects all layers of society and requires complex solutions to ensure economic stability.

State policy: ways to reduce unemployment and legal aspects: Measures taken by the state to reduce unemployment are important. In the experience of Uzbekistan, the following measures are taken to reduce unemployment:

1. Vocational training and skills development: New jobs will be created by improving the skills of the population for the development of entrepreneurship. Within the framework of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Vocational Education", attention is focused on the development of skills required in the labor market. Through this, the population's employment opportunities will be expanded.
2. Support for startups: Creating new jobs in the private sector by promoting new business projects. The state supports young entrepreneurs through the "Youth - Towards the Future" program, which creates new jobs. Also, the state organizes projects for the promotion of innovative ideas, such as "InnoWeek".
3. Improving the education system: Expanding professional opportunities through education and training programs. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 137 dated March 16, 2020 aim to increase professional knowledge and organize qualification exams at the level of demand.
4. Regulating the labor market: expanding labor migration and creating jobs in order to reduce unemployment. Through the Law "On Labor Migration" of Uzbekistan, the system of employment of workers abroad and creation of jobs in the country is being developed.

The legal basis for the implementation of the state policy against unemployment is also important. The issue of unemployment in Uzbekistan is regulated in accordance with the labor rights and constitutional guarantees of citizens. The following legal documents are the basis for the implementation of legal relations:

1. Laws on the protection of labor rights of citizens: the rights of workers are protected by the Labor Code, the Law "On the Protection of Labor Rights of Citizens" and other laws regulating labor relations.
2. International agreements on combating unemployment: international legal agreements signed by Uzbekistan, such as International Labor Organization (ILO) conventions, set global standards in the field of employment, skill development and professional training.

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3. The system of providing employment through state programs and projects: the employment of the population is controlled through state programs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including projects such as "Development of Vocational Education", "Ishga Merhamat". The legal basis is necessary to ensure the stability of the fight against unemployment. Because legal regulations create a basis for the implementation of state policies and economic programs. Norms for wages, professional training, labor contracts and organization of workplaces have also been established. Through these legal relations, it is possible to ensure employment of the citizen, to guarantee justice and equal opportunities in employment.

Such comprehensive approaches implemented by the government of Uzbekistan serve to reduce unemployment and increase the employment of the population.

Experiences on an international scale: Unemployment is one of the important issues that need to be solved for economic and social development worldwide. The goal of strengthening economic stability by ensuring employment of the population is also set for international countries. To this end, different countries have different experiences in implementing their measures aimed at reducing unemployment.

1. Germany

Germany pays great attention to vocational education and training. Through the vocational training system, young people and the existing workforce will have opportunities for quality improvement. At the same time, the state provides subsidies for enterprises and innovative projects, as a result of which new jobs are created.

2. South Korea

South Korea has developed special programs aimed at reducing youth and female unemployment for economic growth. Through the state policy on youth and gender equality, a fair environment is created in the labor market. Also, efforts are being made to create new jobs through high technologies.

3. Australia

Australia is fighting unemployment through vocational education and training programs. Grants and subsidies provided by the state play an important role in supporting small businesses and creating new jobs. High standards have been introduced in labor contracts and work organization.

4. Sweden

In order to reduce unemployment in Sweden, the government focuses on targeted education programs and job training. Efforts are made to create equal opportunities for women and disabled people by ensuring the principles of gender equality.

Various measures are being implemented in Uzbekistan to reduce unemployment based on international experiences. As we have seen above, vocational education by the state, support of start-

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ups and creation of new opportunities for labor migrants are the most important international models. We also mentioned that gender equality, youth unemployment and professional training have a special place in the policy of our country. Through this, economic stability will be achieved in our country and the standard of living of the population will increase.

Conclusion

Unemployment is a pressing problem for every country. It is possible to solve this problem through state policy, international experience and legal regulation of this urgent topic. In Uzbekistan, as in the experience of other countries, measures such as professional training, support for startups, and increasing youth employment are being implemented, and we analyzed this above through some legislative documents. It is also important to create equal opportunities for all segments of the population by strengthening the legal framework.

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